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DEVELOPMENT OF A WIND POWER PLANT MODEL FOR SIMULATION MODELING

Citation: M.M. Hamdamov.
Development of a wind power
plant model for simulation
modeling. Journal of Hydraulics
and Environmental Engineering
(JHEE) 2024, 2(1).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10700345>

Academic Editors: Aybek
Arifjanov

Received: 25.01.2024
Revised: 30.01.2024
Accepted: 30.02.2024
Published: 19.02.2024

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M.M. Hamdamov^{1,2*}

¹Institute of Mechanics and Seismic Stability of Structures named after
M.T.Urazbaev, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

² Oriental University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

*Corresponding author: mmhamdamov@mail.ru

Abstract. Developing a Model for VAWT The computer model developed in this work is designed to simulate what happens in a physical environment. The mathematical equations presented in the previous work [13] were translated into a system in the MATLAB Simulink program. This one has a simple interface that allows you to see the calculations in a block diagram and clearly illustrates the structure of the model. General structure The model is shown in Figure 1. This model will be used in the future to determine the values of the tangential direction of flow in the blades of a wind generator and the moment of its rotation.

Keywords: Wind force, velocity field, MATLAB Simulink, block diagram, mathematical model of wind turbine.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a set of measures aimed at further increasing the efficiency of the use of electrical energy in economic sectors and in everyday life, the widespread introduction of energy-efficient technologies and the development of renewable energy sources.

Over the past 50 years, 85% of the share of electricity generation in the republic corresponds to natural gas [1-5]. Carbon dioxide and carbon oxides emitted as a result of the combustion of hydrocarbons lead to atmospheric pollution, a decrease in its transparency and an increase in turbidity. This, in turn, intensifies the “greenhouse effect”, which over the past hundred years has increased the average temperature of the Earth’s atmosphere by 1.5-2 degrees. Such global climate change leads to the melting of glaciers at the north and south poles of the Earth and the frequent formation of anomalous climatic phenomena. Ultimately, this affects the global

ecological state of the planet and the development of civilization. In this regard, today the widespread use of alternative sources of electricity is becoming relevant.

Of the alternative sources of electricity, the cheapest and most environmentally feasible is the driving force of wind, which has a high economic indicator. Based on these judgments, we developed a prototype of a wind turbine with a vertical axis, which can operate at low wind speeds and which can be installed in many regions of the republic.

Large-scale work is underway in the Republic of Uzbekistan to support energy independence. Exploration work is being carried out to identify new fields and measures are being taken to increase the volume of development of oil and gas fields. They began to build a nuclear power plant. The introduction of alternative renewable sources of electricity is gradually developing. They began to build solar and wind power plants.

The model of the wind power plant was developed with a predetermined KIEV of the wind turbine and a universal controller to ensure the possibility of changing the control algorithm; the functional diagram of the model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Functional diagram of a wind power plant model

The software package for mathematical calculations MATLAB/Simulink from Mathworks Inc, widely used both in the scientific community and in various design organizations, was chosen as the development and research environment [6-8].

The MATLAB/Simulink package is based on the MATLAB solver with its own shell [5-10]. This solver allows you to perform complex mathematical calculations with various objects: numbers, vectors, matrices, as well as solve systems of equations of varying complexity. To facilitate the process of modeling various systems, in addition to the solver, Mathworks Inc has developed a Simulink add-on containing a large library of models of various devices. Moreover, the proposed models contain a mathematical description given in the documentation for the library. However, when developing control systems, not only models of control objects are required, but also a model of the control device, and its complexity usually varies from task to task, which creates a request for a universal approach to developing a model of the control device.

Figure 2. Simplified program model showing inputs and feedback loops

In most cases, modern modeling tools make it possible to ensure a high level of model adequacy. One such tool is Simulink, an interactive tool for modeling, simulating and analyzing dynamic systems. It makes it possible to build graphical block diagrams, simulate dynamic systems, examine system performance, and improve designs. Simulink is fully integrated with the MATLAB application package, providing access to a wide range of analysis and design tools [9-11].

The model input variables are divided into two categories:

- design parameters of the installation (maximum and minimum diameters of the wind wheel, maximum and minimum width of the blades, number of blades, moment of inertia, optimal angle of attack, aerodynamic coefficients of the wing profile);
- independent input variables (wind speed, air density, load moment on the shaft, wing installation angle (pitch)...).

Description of coefficient dependencies C_y and C_x from angle of attack (α) is generated within the model using a Lagrange interpolation polynomial.

The undoubted advantages of the model include the ability to study transient regimes that arise when the wind speed and load on the main shaft changes. Our mathematical model:

Figure 3. Block diagram implementing the mathematical model of wind turbines

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Turbine power is determined by the following equation

$$P_m = \frac{1}{2} C_p(\lambda, \beta) \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot V_w^3$$

Here:

P_m - mechanical turbine power output (w), $C_p(\lambda, \beta)$ - Turbine efficiency, ρ - air density (kg/m^3), A - turbine surface (m^2), V_w - wind speed (m/s), λ - ratio of rotor blade tip speed to wind speed, β - blade angle

$$C_p(\lambda, \beta) = c_1 \left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda_i} - c_3 \cdot \beta - c_4 \cdot \beta^x - c_5 \right) \exp\left(-\frac{c_6}{\lambda_i}\right)$$

Here $c_1, c_2 \dots c_6$ they don't change.

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i} = \frac{1}{\lambda + 0.08\beta} - \frac{0.035}{1 + \beta^3}$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\omega_r \cdot R}{V_w}$$

We are designing a 2 kW wind turbine. For this we use the following values [10-17]:

λ	1-45
$C_p(\lambda, \beta)$	0.3-0.4
V_w	1-20 m/c
R	3
c_1	0.5
c_2	116
c_3	0.4
c_4	0
c_5	5
c_6	21

$C_p(\lambda, \beta)$ we expect:

Figure 4. Block diagram $C_p(\lambda, \beta)$

Figure 6. Schematic of a complete MATLAB model for wind turbines

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A numerical experiment was carried out using this block diagram. The main purpose of this is to determine the optimal parameters of the turbine. Initially, $C_p=0.3$ was accepted. In this case, the rotation speed was taken to be 67 per minute. With these values, the following results were obtained for cases where $\omega = 7$.

Figure 7. Dependence of generator load torque on λ

Figure 8. Dependence λ on wind speed

Figure 9. Wind speed dependence of the idle generator

Figure 10. Dependence of the generator no-load moment on λ

A numerical experiment was carried out using this block diagram. The main purpose of this is to determine the optimal parameters of the turbine. Initially, $C_p=0.35$ was assumed. In this case, the rotation speed was taken to be 67 per minute. With these values, the following results were obtained for cases where $\omega = 7$.

Figure 11. Dependence of generator load torque on λ

Figure 12. Dependence of the generator no-load moment on λ

Figure 13. Wind speed dependence of the idle generator

Figure 14. Dependence of generator load torque on wind speed

A numerical experiment was carried out using this block diagram. The main purpose of this is to determine the optimal parameters of the turbine. Initially, $C_p=0.40$ was assumed. In this case, the rotation speed was taken to be 67 per minute. With these values, the following results were obtained for cases where $\omega = 7$.

Figure 15. Dependence of generator load torque on wind speed

Figure 16. Dependence of generator no-load moment on wind speed

Figure 17. Dependence of the generator no-load moment on λ

Figure 18. Dependence of generator load torque on λ

A numerical experiment was carried out using this block diagram. The main purpose of this is to determine the optimal parameters of the turbine. Initially, $C_p=0.40$ was assumed. In this case, the rotation speed was taken to be 96 per minute. With these values, the following results were obtained for cases where $\omega = 10$.

Figure 19. Dependence of generator load torque on wind speed

Figure 20. Dependence of generator no-load moment on wind speed

Figure 21. Dependence λ on wind speed

Figure 22. Dependence of generator load torque on λ

A numerical experiment was carried out using this block diagram. The main purpose of this is to determine the optimal parameters of the turbine. Initially, $C_p=0.40$ was assumed. In this case, the rotation speed was taken to be 120 per minute. With these values, the following results were obtained for cases where $\omega = 12.56$.

Figure 23. Dependence of generator no-load moment on wind speed

Figure 24. Dependence of the generator no-load moment on λ

Figure 25. Dependence of the generator no-load moment on λ

Figure 26. Dependence on λ wind speed

A numerical experiment was carried out using this block diagram. The main purpose of this is to determine the optimal parameters of the turbine. Initially, $C_p=0.40$ was assumed. In this case, the rotation speed was taken to be 150 per minute. With these values, the following results were obtained for cases where $\omega = 15.7$.

Figure 27. Dependence of generator no-load moment on wind speed

Figure 28. Dependence of generator load torque on wind speed

Figure 29. Dependence on λ wind speed

Figure 30. Dependence of the generator no-load moment on λ

A numerical experiment was carried out using this block diagram. The main purpose of this is to determine the optimal parameters of the turbine. Initially, $C_p=0.40$ was assumed. In this case, the rotation speed was taken to be 96 per minute. With these values, the following results were obtained for cases where $\omega = 15.7$.

Figure 31. Dependence of the generator no-load moment on λ

Figure 32. Dependence of generator load torque on λ

Figure 33. Dependence of generator load torque on wind speed

Figure 34. Dependence of generator no-load moment on wind speed

4 CONCLUSION

The results of a computational experiment on the dynamics of wind turbines were used in the development of a microprocessor control system. Using the model, the optimal control law was determined and an adaptive automatic control system for the wind power complex was developed, which allows increasing its energy efficiency.

The developed model makes it possible, given the known design parameters of the wind turbine, to obtain mechanical and energy characteristics for various wind speeds, optimal combinations of blade pitch values, rotation speed and load torque, and a control law that ensures maximum wind energy efficiency.

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